

2:BRF

2nd Balkan Rhino-Forum Sinusitis, Skull Base & Rhinoplasty Symposium

in conjunction with 4th Symposium of
Rhinology & Allergy Association of Serbia [RAAS]

Belgrade, Serbia, hotel Metropol Palace
04-06 APRIL 2019

PROGRAM and ABSTRACT eBOOK

Organizing Committee

Aleksandar Perić, MD, PhD,
Assistant Professor of Otorhinolaryngology, Department of
Otorhinolaryngology, Military Medical Academy Faculty of
Medicine, University of Defence, Belgrade, Serbia,
President of Rhinology & Allergy Association of Serbia –
President of Organizing and Scientific Committee

Ljiljana Jovančević, MD, PhD,
Assistant Professor of Otorhinolaryngology, Clinic for
Diseases of Ear, Nose and Throat, Clinical Center of
Vojvodina, Novi Sad, Serbia, Secretary of Rhinology &
Allergy Association of Serbia

Rajko Jović, MD, PhD,
Professor of Otorhinolaryngology, Clinic for Diseases of
Ear, Nose and Throat, Clinical Center of Vojvodina, Novi
Sad, Serbia, President of ENT Section of the Serbian
Medical Society

Aleksandra Barać, MD, PhD,
Scientific Associate, Clinical Center of Serbia, School of
Medicine, Belgrade, Serbia, Honorary Professor, University
of Sassari, Italy

Jelena Sotirović, MD, PhD,
Department of Otorhinolaryngology, Military Medical
Academy Faculty of Medicine, University of Defence,
Belgrade, Serbia

Uglješa Grgurević, MD,
Department of Otorhinolaryngology, Military Medical
Academy Faculty of Medicine, University of Defence,
Belgrade, Serbia

International Scientific Committee

Wytske Fokkens, MD, PhD,
Professor of Otorhinolaryngology, Department of
Otorhinolaryngology, Academic Medical Center,
Amsterdam, The Netherlands

Sarah K. Wise, MD, PhD,
Professor of Otorhinolaryngology, Emory University,
Atlanta, USA

Nicolas Busaba, MD, PhD,
Professor of Otorhinolaryngology, Harvard Medical School
and Massachusetts Eye and Ear, Boston, USA

John DelGaudio, MD, PhD,
Professor of Otorhinolaryngology, Emory University,
Atlanta, USA

Sergei Karpischenko, MD, PhD,
Professor of Otorhinolaryngology, First Pavlov Saint
Petersburg State Medical University, Saint Petersburg,
Russia

Jannis Constantinidis, MD, PhD,
Professor of Otorhinolaryngology, Aristotle University,
Thessaloniki, Greece

Christos Georgalas, MD, PhD,
Professor of Surgery/Head and Neck, University of
Nicosia/Program of St. Georges Medical School, Director of
Endoscopic Skull Base Hygeia Hospital, Athens, Greece

Gabriela Kopacheva Barsova, MD, PhD,
Assistant Professor of Otorhinolaryngology, ENT -
University Hospital, University Campus "St. Mother
Theresa" Skopje, Republic of North Macedonia

Marc Scheithauer, MD, PhD,
Professor of Otorhinolaryngology, Department of
Otorhinolaryngology, Head and Neck Surgery University
Hospital of Ulm, Ulm, Germany

Rajko Jović, MD, PhD,
Professor of Otorhinolaryngology, Clinic for Diseases of
Ear, Nose and Throat, Clinical Center of Vojvodina, Medical
Faculty, University of Novi Sad, Novi Sad, Serbia

Livije Kalogjera, MD, PhD,
Professor of Otorhinolaryngology, School of Medicine in
Zagreb, University Hospital „Sestre Milosrdnice“, Zagreb,
Croatia

Tomislav Baudoin, MD, PhD,
Professor of Otorhinolaryngology, School of Medicine in
Zagreb, University Hospital „Sestre Milosrdnice“, Zagreb,
Croatia

Dilyana Vicheva, MD, PhD,
Professor of Otorhinolaryngology, Medical University of
Plovdiv, Plovdiv, Bulgaria

Aleksandar Perić, MD, PhD,
Assistant Professor of Otorhinolaryngology, Department of
Otorhinolaryngology, Military Medical Academy Faculty of
Medicine, University of Defence, Belgrade, Serbia

EUROPEAN RHINOLOGIC
SOCIETY

RHINOLOGY & ALLERGY
ASSOCIATION OF SERBIA

SERBIAN MEDICAL SOCIETY

2:BRF

2nd Balkan Rhino-Forum
Sinusitis, Skull Base & Rhinoplasty Symposium

in conjunction with 4th Symposium of
RhinoLOGY & Allergy Association of Serbia [RAAS]

04-06 April 2019 • Hotel Metropol Palace, Belgrade, Serbia

Ljiljana Jovančević, MD, PhD,
Assistant Professor of Otorhinolaryngology, Clinic for
Diseases of Ear, Nose and Throat, Clinical Center of
Vojvodina, Medical Faculty, University of Novi Sad, Novi
Sad, Serbia

Aleksandra Barać, MD, PhD,
Scientific Associate, Clinical Center of Serbia, School of
Medicine, Belgrade, Serbia, Honorary Professor, University
of Sassari, Italy

Technical organizer:

MedApp • e-mail: brfbelgrade@gmail.com • Phone: +381 64 5281 658

ANTIBIOTIC TREATMENT OF ACUTE SINUSITIS IN PRIMARY HEALTH CARE IN NOVI SAD, SERBIA

Nemanja Todorović¹, Tamara Tešić^{2,3}, Maja Buljčik-Čupić^{2,3}, Nataša Milošević¹, Boris Milijašević⁴, Mladena Lalić-Popović¹

¹University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Medicine Novi Sad, Department of Pharmacy, Novi Sad, Republic of Serbia

²Clinical Centre of Vojvodina, Clinic for Ear, Nose and Throat Diseases, Novi Sad, Republic of Serbia

³University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Medicine Novi Sad, Department of Otorhinolaryngology, Novi Sad, Republic of Serbia

⁴University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Medicine Novi Sad, Department of Pharmacology and Toxicology, Novi Sad, Republic of Serbia

Background: Reducing bacterial resistance to antibiotics requires the creation of and adherence to detailed guidelines. The aim of this study was to examine the adherence of prescribed antibiotics for the treatment of acute sinusitis to guidelines that existed at the time of prescribing the drugs.

Methods: Data were collected during January 2018 in seven pharmacies (Health Institution Pharmacy "Cvejić") on the territory of Novi Sad. Realized antibiotic prescriptions were analyzed, and data of interest were: gender, age, diagnosis and prescribed therapy. The adherence of the prescribing practice to the guidelines given by the Republic Health Insurance Fund from 2014 was verified. Data analysis was performed using the Microsoft Excel software for Windows.

Results: In the observed period, 1315 prescriptions were realized, of which 734 (5.60 %) were antibiotic. Acute sinusitis was the fifth most common diagnosis for which antibiotics were prescribed and a total of 34 patients were diagnosed with this infection: 25 women with the average age of 47.64 ± 14.44 years (range 14-69 years), eight men with the average age of 38.75 ± 19.20 years (range 14-68 years) and one child seven years old. Eighteen prescriptions (52.94 %) were in accordance with the guidelines. In 11 recipes (35.35 %) drugs that were not listed in the guidelines (levofloxacin, doxycycline, clindamycin and co-trimoxazole) were identified. In five prescriptions (14.70 %) the prescribed dose was not adequate: four prescriptions (11.76 %) prescribed subminimal doses of the drug, and in one prescription (2.94 %) the dose exceeded the maximum prescribed dose for the overall treatment of the infection.

Conclusions: The study shows low adherence to the guidelines when prescribing antibiotics for the treatment of acute sinusitis. Although following the guidelines when prescribing drugs is not obligatory, it can contribute to reducing the resistance of bacteria to antibiotics.